

General Topology Based on Zermelo's Axioms

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Abstract

The fact that for any correctly defined function there exists the image of the domain of this function under this function is commonly accepted by those who use system of axiom based on Zermelo's postulates – Z . But this fact applied in literal meaning leads to strange consequences. We show some of them related to general topology in Z or ZF (Zermelo–Fraenkel's axioms). Just topology in Z or ZF seems to be impossible.

System of Ernst Zermelo's postulates we can find in [1] both in German and also in English as the verbatim English translation. The base for our deliberations is the version of axioms presented in [2]. Topological spaces and subspaces are discussed in [3].

1 Introduction

First of all we have to admit that in Z (and related system of axioms) any set is determined by its own elements. There is no other elements in any set then all its own elements – and these elements create that set. If we define the function α on set A then A is the domain of α . There exist, for sure, the image of A under the function α – denoted as $\alpha(A)$. This set must contain images of each one element of A and no one element of A can be missing. It applies to any function and its domain – also (*sic!*) when this domain is a chain without the last element or without the first element (e.g. the set \mathbb{N} or an open real interval). There is no element in the domain A for which the value of the function α (defined on A) does not exist or this value is not the element of the set $\alpha(A)$.

$$\{x \in A \mid \alpha(x) \notin \alpha(A)\} = \emptyset,$$

$$\{x \in A \mid \alpha(x) \in \alpha(A)\} = A.$$

We cannot find or create in A any element whose image is not already in $\alpha(A)$. If we could create or find such an element it would be – due to *Axiom of Extensionality* – quite another set then A . It is easy – "all elements" means exactly all – no one less, no one more.

Some consequences of this above applied to the set \mathbb{N} (as a chain without the last element) are shown in [4] and [5].

2 Topology in Z or ZF

Let $J = [0, 1]$ be a closed-closed real interval and $\mathbb{P}(J)$ be the powerset of J – the set of all subsets of J . $\mathbb{P}(J) = \mathbb{P}([0, 1])$.

Let us define the function t on $[0, 1) \subsetneq [0, 1]$ as follows:

$$[0, 1) \ni x \longrightarrow t(x) = (J \setminus [0, x]) \in \mathbb{P}([0, 1]).$$

The domain of t – denoted as D_t – is the closed-open interval $[0, 1)$. Obviously

$$\forall_{x \in D_t} t(x) \subset J = [0, 1] \quad \text{and} \quad \forall_{x \in D_t} t(x) = J \setminus [0, x] = [0, 1] \setminus [0, x].$$

The elements of D_t are all elements of $[0, 1]$ except the number 1. Thus each one $x \in [0, 1]$ is either an element of the domain of the function t or is the number 1. There is no other elements in J . We have as well

$$\forall_{x \in D_t} x \notin t(x) \quad \text{and} \quad \forall_{x \in D_t} t(x) \cap [0, x] = \emptyset$$

– because in any difference of two sets there is no any element of a subtrahend.

We can be sure that there exists $t(D_t)$ – the image of the domain D_t under the function t – and this set contains values of the function t calculated for all elements of D_t with no any exception, i.e. $\{x \in D_t \mid t(x) \in t(D_t)\} = D_t$.

The set $t(D_t)$ must really exist and must really contain all its own elements.

The argument of the function t is always the right end (the biggest element) of the subtracted interval. The only element of $J = [0, 1]$ that is not any element of D_t is the number 1. Only the number 1 is not the right end of any subtracted intervals – each other element of $J = [0, 1]$ really is.

Since $t(D_t)$ contains all differences $J \setminus [0, x]$, for all(!) $x \in D_t$, then $t(D_t)$ must contain, as its own element, a set that:

- is the subset of J ,
- does not contain any element of D_t .

The only such a set is the set $\{1\}$. But $\{1\} = [1, 1]$. This way $[1, 1] \in t(D_t)$.

It means that

$$\exists_{x_0 \in D_t} t(x_0) = [1, 1]$$

or, in other form

$$\exists_{x_0 \in D_t} [0, 1] \setminus [0, x_0] = [1, 1]. \tag{1}$$

All three intervals: $[0, 1]$, $[0, x_0]$ and $[1, 1]$ are closed-closed real intervals.

\mathbb{R} with the usual topology based on open-open intervals is a topological space.

Let us regard J as the topological subspace of \mathbb{R} with the inherited topology:

- two intervals: $[0, x_0]$ and $[1, 1]$ are closed sets in J , due to rules of the topology of the topological subspace (e.g. [3], ch. 3).
- no one of these two intervals is the open set in J , for the same reasons, mentioned previously,
- the set $[1, 1]$ is the complement of $[0, x_0]$ in J .

This is absolutely impossible! But it is a must, because $t(D_t)$ exists and contains images of all elements of D_t – no one element of D_t is missing.

3 By the way

The sentence (1) can be also interpret in a bit different way.

$[0, 1] \setminus [0, x_0] = [1, 1] = \{1\}$, so $[0, 1] \setminus \{1\} = [0, x_0]$. But also $[0, 1] \setminus \{1\} = [0, 1)$. Two sets $[0, x_0]$ and $[0, 1)$ have the same elements, so they are the same set. Just

$$[0, x_0] = [0, 1).$$

The first interval is closed-closed, the second is closed-open. Impossible.

The first interval has the last element, the second has not. Impossible.

Impossible since both intervals are the same set.

What is more – the real number 1 is the next element to the real number x_0 , because $\neg \exists_{x \in [0, 1]} (x \neq 1 \wedge x \notin [0, x_0])$. Something like "a real successor". Impossible as well.

4 Conclusions

In Zermelo's set of axioms (and ZF) general topology is impossible.

Neither Z nor ZF should be used as the foundations for mathematics any longer in the form as they are nowadays. It leads to absurd consequences.

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References

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